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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 6.3 – VALIDATION AND EVALUATION (FIRST VERSION)

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Author(s)	Andrea Alesani, Kaj Helin Timo Kuula, Sebastian Lorenz, Daniel Röck, Volker Waurich
Contact details of the coordinator	Martijn Rooker, martijn.rooker@tttech.com
Internal Reviewer	Anastasia Sergeeva (UL) Martijn Rooker (TTC)

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the conducted validation and evaluation activities during the project. These activities aim to optimize the fit of our developed extended reality (XR) technologies to our key performance indicators (KPIs) set to guide development towards applicable and effective solutions. The KPIs comprise (1) improved safety (for operator, vehicle, cargo and personnel in the area of operation), (2) reassured usability, (3) consideration of privacy, and (4) improved quality of work. This first version reports on the state of prototypes used for evaluation and already conducted evaluation activities across all three use cases.

This comprises testing a panoramic thermal-RGB camera, a camera-based spotlight system, and a novel laser-camera setup, temporarily installed on a snow groomer, a haptic device demonstrator workshop, the testing and evaluation of a display-based VR control environment for teleoperation, the evaluation of augmenting visualizations of surface mappings, the evaluation of visual representations in an ambient light system, and the testing of visual styles, visibility and assistive performance of a tool-mounted matrix display. So far, the standardized System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire, semi-structured group interviews, focusing on the usability and usefulness of the system, and observations were used to gather feedback on the prototyped XR technologies and interaction features. The user tests consisted of system introduction and training for the users, actual test task performance, and data collection part including questionnaire and group interview.

The conducted evaluation activities overall confirmed the usefulness of our approaches for cabin-based and remote operation of mobile machines. Technical functionality and feasibility could be established for almost all prototypes, except the laser projection test in broad daylight in the excavator tests.

This deliverable further outlines planned improvements regarding our XR interaction concepts and prototypes and upcoming evaluation measures in the second half of the project.

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1 Introduction

The Validation and evaluation methodology was already developed and documented in deliverable D3.5. Validation and evaluation criteria are derived from the original project proposal and deliverables D2.1 and D2.2. This deliverable gives a brief overview in section 2.

Applying this procedure, our validation and evaluation efforts cover (i) controlled lab-based experiments for evaluating of the developed technologies and methodologies of THEIA^{XR}, (ii) trials of the XR and human-machine interaction applications of the 3 use cases in relevant environment, and (iii) a cross checking to assess the generality of the THEIA^{XR} technologies and methodologies.

To this date, as the first version of this deliverable is submitted, use case and requirement analysis as well as technology and interaction concept development already led to first prototypes and demonstrators that were used to evaluate different qualities and performance predictors in small expert groups and pilot studies. In further extending functional depth of these demonstrators in the coming months, larger scale evaluations also involving end users are currently planned. Conducted activities as well as planned evaluation procedures are elaborated for each use case separately in chapters 3, 4, and 5 of this deliverable.

This section is reporting three development cycles, each yielding functional prototypes. The work has been done in close co-operation with WP3 where XR interaction sequences were compiled (see D3.2), privacy relate questions were discussed (see D3.3), and prototypes were developed (see D3.4, where a more detailed descriptions of the prototypes can be found). Results of the first evaluation activities also contributed to detail and further specify our use cases (see D2.4) and technology requirements (see D2.5).

2 Design and evaluation methods

2.1 General procedure

Creating prototypes of different fidelities and their evaluation across many phases of technology development is an integral part of the iterative design strategy that THEIA^{XR} applies. According to the associated ISO standard, the basic design cycle consists of the following phases: Understanding the context of use, specifying user requirements, producing design solutions, and evaluating the design (ISO 9241-210) [2]. Each phase informs the other as well as proposing feedback loops to iterate earlier steps to gradually improve interaction concepts and technology towards a desired or acceptable quality (see Figure 1).

In all three use cases and associated technology development workgroups, the design process started by quickly analysing the most important features of the involved machines and their involvement to produce a quick-and-dirty prototype that users could try and evaluate in a first pilot test. From there, redesign phases are conducted, updating the initial requirements, improving existing solutions and developing new features. So far, requirements, potential XR technologies as well as hypothetic interaction sequences have been assessed and compiled, leading to the development of first prototypes for each use case (see D2.2, D4.3 and D3.4) the technologies that integrated in these prototypes (see D6.1) and their planned deployment in overall demonstrators (see D6.2)

So far, most prototypes are pushed towards their first user test phase, after being evaluated and advanced within the project teams. This deliverable recalls identified issues, evaluation procedures and measures and report on the already conducted, ongoing and planned activities across all three use cases.

Figure 1: The project starts with an initial prototype and a pilot test. Then, a cyclical process of improvements and evaluations brings to the final version.

2.2 Use Case Issues, KPIS and Measurement approaches

The original project proposal listed several KPIs that each use case applied in parts according to the selected development focus. These KPIs are listed in Table 1 on page 9.

#	General KPIs
1	Improve safety for operator, vehicle and nearby skiers or other civilians
2	Reassure good usability
3	Consider privacy relations
4	Improve quality of work

Table 1: General KPIs for XR technologies and their integration in user interfaces

These KPIs were elaborated in an initial requirement analysis phase, elaborating on these KPIs by identifying operation and performance issues. Tables 2, 3 and 4 summarize the findings of deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 in this regard.

#	Issues in Use Case 1 – Snow grooming
1	How to visualize the required information to the operator?
2	Due to limited view around the vehicle, it is hard to see/detect obstacles around.
3	Operator needs to work also in complete “whiteout” with no view.
4	With no view it is not possible to detect obstacles with the eyes.

Table 2: KPI-related issues in the snow grooming use case

#	Issues in Use Case 2 – Logistics
1	Visibility to target position and container
2	Visibility to obstacles around the machine
3	Distances between objects
4	Trailer twist locks can get stuck
5	Material damages
6	Safety (persons around the machine and other vehicles)
7	Productivity of the remote-controlled system
8	Latency and reliability of the communication

Table 3: KPI-related issues in the logistics use case

#	Issues in Use Case 3 - Construction
1	The operator’s view on the attachment and the graphical user interface are not in one visual axis.
2	Current 3D-machine control interfaces offer a visual display of target and actual bucket height. It hardly allows a comprehensive view of the entire work area to plan e.g., backfilling.
3	Current operation requires confident usage and understanding of 3D-machine control systems and confidence in proper alignment of 3D-model to real world.
4	Spatial imagination to align the abstract, virtual reference model with real references.
5	Infield design requires a spatial imagination to design profile and outline with reference to the real environment.
6	Collision Warning Systems (CWS) often annoy the operator due to the high frequency of warnings. This leads to deactivation of CWS.

Table 4: KPI-related issues in the construction use case

The conducted analysis identified five key factors suitable to evaluate the impact of the developed technologies and their implementation in XR interaction concept. The assessment of these KPIs is conceptualized in Deliverable D3.5. The following table gives a summary of related criteria, methods and measures.

#	Key Factors/Criteria addressing the identified KPIs	
1	Safety	<p>Improved safety for operator, vehicle and persons and objects in vicinity (UC1, UC2, UC3): Safety is often referred to be the most important operational criteria and refers to design and functional features that help to prevent accidents, machine abuse and operational errors. The higher the operational safety of a system is the lower the probabilities are these to occur.</p> <p>Can be measures through: A1: The operators' situation awareness regarding potential safety threats, and A2: The operators' safety-related behaviour (e.g. regularly checking for obstacles in the environment)</p>
2	Usability	<p>Usability is the extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use. Usability refers to the ease with which people can use a product or system to achieve their goals effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily.</p> <p>Can be measures through: B1: The System Usability Scale [4], and B2: The usability components of the UEQ+ questionnaire (e.g., efficiency, usefulness, intuitive use, novelty, trust, quality of content, or comprehensibility) [7]. B3: INTUI, a validated 17-item questionnaire that focus intuitivity of a system [8]. B4: Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use scale (PUEU), a validated 14+14-item scale focusing the measurement of usefulness and perceived ease of use [9].</p>
3	Quality of work	<p>The concept of quality of work refers to the standard of excellence exhibited in tasks, projects, or output produced by individuals or teams within a professional context. It encompasses various aspects, including accuracy, completeness, effectiveness, efficiency, reliability, and consistency.</p> <p>Can be measures through: C1: Time on Task, and (explicit measures) C2: Accuracy of task execution (explicit measures)</p>
4	Situation awareness	<p>Situation awareness refers to the understanding and perception of the environment and the dynamic elements within it, including events, objects, people, and their interactions. It involves being aware of relevant information, predicting future developments, and making effective decisions based on this understanding.</p> <p>Can be measures through: D1: SPAM - A query-based SA measurement method. In this method, the operator is presented with queries about the situation while the situation remains present and while the operator performs primary tasks [10].</p>
5	Acceptance:	<p>Technology acceptance refers to the willingness and readiness of individuals or groups to adopt and use a new technology. It involves understanding the factors that influence users' perceptions and attitudes toward technology adoption, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and other social and organizational factors.</p> <p>Can be measures through: According to the technology acceptance model, acceptance cannot be measured upon initial use. However, it has been shown to rely on precursors such as usefulness, usability, satisfaction (positive UX), ease of use, trust, or perceived risk [11]. We argue to use the measures above to discuss an acceptance tendency towards the evaluated concepts.</p>

Table 5: Evaluation criteria and approaches to their measurement

The following sections briefly recall the state of prototypes followed by reporting on conducted, ongoing and planned evaluation activities and results.

3 Use case 1 – Snow grooming

3.1 Introduction

The operation of a snow groomer is becoming increasingly challenging due to the growing amount of information that the operator must take care of, coupled with the difficulties posed by the environment around the vehicle. Despite this, additional information can be used to support the operator in their guidance and operation of the vehicle even in challenging conditions. The operational environment incorporates various weather conditions, such as sun, rain, snowfall, ice rain, fog, and wind, both individually and in combination, ranging from -35°C up to 20°C, which greatly increases the operator's workload.

By incorporating Extended Reality (XR) technologies that can provide information in more natural and intuitive ways, it is possible to address the challenges associated with snow groomer operation. These technologies have the potential to significantly reduce the operator's workload and improve usability. By using augmented reality or virtual reality solutions, for example, it is possible to provide the operator with real-time data overlays that do not require them to take their hands off the controls or look away from the surroundings. This can help to alleviate some of the issues of distraction and situational awareness that are commonly associated with snow groomer operation. Overall, these augmenting XR technologies offer substantial potential for enhancing the safety, comfort, and efficiency of snow groomer operation.

Application of KPIs

KPI 1.1 (improved safety for operator, vehicle and nearby skiers or other civilians):

Snow grooming operation presents a challenging scenario due to difficult environmental conditions with low visibility while navigating around obstacles. These factors create significant safety hazards for both the operator and others nearby. The snow groomer operator cannot interact directly with the available data due to the need to always keep their hands on the controls. In addition, the lack of visibility surrounding the vehicle can lead to hazardous situations. To address these challenges, the proposed technology solution will incorporate augmented reality or virtual reality technologies, providing the snow groomer operator with real-time, non-distracting data overlays that require minimal attention but are visible in the field of view. This approach will improve situational awareness for the operator while also providing a better experience. The effectiveness of these concepts will be evaluated by comparing the baseline (status quo) measurements of perceived presence, awareness, and responsibility with those of the prototypes.

KPI 1.2 (reassured usability):

The task of operating a snow groomer is increasingly difficult due to the amount of information that operators need to manage continuously. The environment surrounding the snow groomer is also becoming more complex to navigate, which adds to the difficulty of the task. As a result, there is a need to develop a technology solution that simplifies the interaction with additional data and the environment using intuitive visualizations and methods that are familiar to operators. To address these challenges, the proposed technology solutions need to provide intuitive and easy ways to navigate and present additional digital data using more familiar visual cues using XR technologies, simplifying interaction with less complex interaction and more comprehensible visualization techniques. The reassured usability of the technology solution will be evaluated by comparing the ease of use and practicality of the XR prototypes with the current machine operation. The evaluation will also involve collecting feedback from operators and stakeholders to optimize the design iteratively. By enhancing the usability of the technology solution, operators can perform the task more efficiently, effectively, and safely while improving the overall quality and performance of snow groomer operation.

KPI 4.1 (consideration of privacy):

To address safety concerns related to snow groomer operation, a preliminary analysis has been conducted to increase awareness and identify potential hazards. Additionally, privacy standards and guidelines will be implemented as part of Work Package 3 (WP3) to ensure the protection of sensitive information. This process involves the application of privacy checklists and guidelines to verify compliance with high privacy standards.

By carefully implementing these measures, the project can address safety concerns while protecting privacy and sensitive information related to snow groomer operation.

KPI 4.2 (improved quality of work) for snow-groomer operation in a virtual cabin:

To measure the improvement in the quality of work for the operate, improving the psychological needs fulfilment and positive experiences at work will be evaluated. The perceived increase of at least one point on average in the respective scales for self-efficacy and meaningfulness of work will be assessed in the current work environment and prototype/demonstrator.

3.2 Prototype evaluation

Focus of XR prototypes:

Three novel prototypes, described in D5.1, have been developed and built. The first one is a panoramic thermal-RGB camera to observe the surrounding during operation. As second prototype a camera-based spotlight system has been developed to illuminate people, obstacles or specified potentially hazardous areas. Finally, a novel laser-camera setup has been built for projecting symbols onto snow surface.

First try-outs with the technologies have been performed in the lab, at the campus of the Technical University of Graz (TUG), and in field tests. These already showed remarkable functions and results.

In the latter half of the project, a demonstrator operator cabin will be installed to further enhance the testing and evaluation of snow groomer operation using the developed technology solution. To create a more realistic environment, a 3D representation of the ski resort will be created in a simulation, and the developed technologies will be integrated. This will allow operators to navigate and interact with the technology solution more effectively and accurately. By using original controls in the simulation, the technology solution can more accurately replicate the experience of operating the actual machine. This will enable more effective evaluation of the technology solution and provide operators with the opportunity to test and provide feedback before implementing it in real-life snow groomer operation.

Evaluation activities:

During the testing phase, a panoramic thermal-RGB camera, a camera-based spotlight system, and a novel laser-camera setup were temporarily installed on a snow groomer and tested in the real-life environment at Ridnaun. The goal was to receive feedback on the functionality of the novel prototypes in the alpine environment and confirm the concepts of the developed technologies. The scientific team from TUG controlled all prototypes, which functioned correctly. However, it was noted that the vibrations of the snow groomer during operation needed to be considered for the next generation of improved prototypes. Although the prototypes were limited in use to researchers, snow grooming operators recognized the first positive results even at this early phase of the project. In the second half of the project, exploration of different environmental conditions will provide deeper insights and enable further optimization. While the development of haptic devices has not yet been completed for implementation into a snow groomer, a haptic device demonstrator workshop has been established to showcase the benefit of the technology to the operator and gather their first impressions. For a reliable validation, haptic feedback will be implemented into original controls to optimize the usability and functionality of the technology solution for snow groomer operations.

4 Use case 2 – Logistics

4.1 Introduction

Application of KPIs:

Regarding KPI 1.1 (improved safety for operator, vehicle, cargo and personnel in the area of operation): Implementing XR technologies in teleoperation environment in this use case focus on improving situation awareness though providing more accessible and additional information regarding the machine and the environment. This is considered to directly improve safety for all involved persons, machines and goods.

Regarding KPI 1.2 (reassured usability): Good usability is important for operation performance and acceptance. This use case tackles this KPI by aiming to use XR technologies to implement important information directly into the visual and haptic perception of operators. Especially the way how operators can interact and customize these information visualizations and control options is considered to affect perceived usability of operators.

Regarding KPI 4.1 (consideration of privacy): Preliminary analysis of safety concerns have been conducted to create awareness to this sensitive topic. Checking and ensuring the fulfilment of high privacy standards is ensured within WP3 and involves the application of privacy guidelines and checklists.

Regarding KPI 4.2 (improved quality of work): This KPI is pursued focusing on increasing performance of remote-controlled operation compare with normal manual operation from the cabin and increasing productivity and decrease ergonomics related sick leaves with better usability and situation awareness.

4.2 Prototype evaluation

Focus of XR prototypes:

As visual, acoustic and haptic immersion is a challenge in teleoperation environments, development efforts in use case 2 focus on providing an interactive multimedia representation of the remote controlled partly automated machines. Big projection screens are used to merge different camera streams augmented with available digital data to provide a compact information stream, helping the operator to access more information in an intuitive and less cognitive demanding procedure. In this regard, evaluating what information are needed in what is the best visualization form are key questions in the conducted evaluation activities. This also applies to haptic and acoustic feedback functionalities that may help to increase immersion, providing feedback in ways operators are used to in today's cabin-based operation environments and to reduce complexity of information on the visual channel. As operators may require different information and perspectives in different situations, the capability to adjust visual output to the operator is also an important feature of user interfaces in this use case. This requires novel interaction techniques such as drag and drop functionalities in a HUD-based user interface or gesture control approaches that are investigated in this use case as well.

Evaluation activities:

So far, three evaluation activities were conducted in the XR laboratory of VTT in Tampere (FIN), focussing on different features of the XR operation system. These evaluations utilized (1) the standardized System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire, (2) semi-structured group interviews, focusing on the usability and usefulness of the system, and (3) observation for data collection. The user tests consisted of system introduction and training for the users, actual test task performance, and data collection part including questionnaire and group interview.

1. The first prototype test on May 16, 2023 in VTT's XR laboratory
2. The second prototype test on November 30, 2023 in VTT's XR laboratory

3. The third prototype test on February 27, 2024 in VTT's XR laboratory

The number of test users was four in the first and second test, and five in the final test. All the users were KALMAR's robotics and simulation experts. The test users performed the tests individually according to instructions from the test organizers. After the test performance, the user filled in the questionnaire and then participated in a group interview including all the test users. The users also commented on the system during the test performance. The work related to first and second prototype has also been reported in AHFE conference publication, July 2024 [1]. The results of the following three user tests are reported in this section.

4.2.1 The first prototype evaluation results

The first user evaluation was organised in VTT's XR laboratory with four KALMAR experts as test users on May 16, 2023.

Regarding the first prototype, Mixed Reality was found to be useful for users in specific use cases, such as driving and checking from specific points of view, but it did not seem to help in high-precision tasks, such as aligning twist locks to casting corners. Some users have expressed discomfort when using an HMD, finding it inconvenient to constantly put on and take off. Consequently, they prefer utilizing displays, particularly through AR visualization.

Most users agreed that having preset teleportation points would be beneficial. This feature would help both new and experienced players. For beginners, it would make interacting with the hand menu easier, as they wouldn't have to navigate complex sliders. Instead, they could simply click buttons. For frequent visitors, it would save time by allowing them to quickly select their favourite positions rather than repositioning the camera every time.

One other issue that users found is strictly related to the technicalities of the XR experience, where hand-tracked menus needed to be continually gazed in order to interact with them (otherwise the Ultraleap's cameras would lose the tracking of the hand). This is counterintuitive and cumbersome, as individuals are used to interact with objects while looking at something else (i.e., when driving, users interact with the shift and the steering wheel while looking at the road). The teleportation feature would partially solve this problem, as users would need to click on the virtual menu once, instead of keeping the buttons pressed continuously until they reach the preferred location.

The views from the orthogonal cameras were the most popular way to complete the task. People preferred looking at them on their normal screens rather than adjusting the special XR camera view. This might be because the XR view is new and different, but one thing that emerged to be vital is that is that the XR camera shows a clear picture of one spot, while the regular cameras show everything in the container.

Based on these findings, the main design choices for the next design cycle should prioritize AR-based visualization on the power wall. Furthermore, the system should more focus on pick-and-place of the container rather than driving.

Another important consideration to make about these results is that, while having a complete "digital twin" reconstruction of the scene might have advantages, they are not relevant enough to justify the costs and efforts of recreating a completely virtual scene. A feasible prototype should then focus on real-camera footage, with possible highly specifically targeted reconstructions, such as for the container casting corners.

User feedback was collected both through a System Usability Scale (SUS) survey, and through group interviews. The SUS scores calculated from individual SUS questionnaires represent the system usability [4]. According to validation studies [5], [6], the SUS score starting from 68-70 represents the level of acceptable system usability. Furthermore, the suggested acceptability ranges are: 0-50 not acceptable; 50-70 marginal; 70- acceptable. The SUS questionnaire results do not have statistical significance due to limited number of test users in this study, but they provide insights on usability combined with qualitative interview results.

SUS score average for the first prototype was **59** (N=4). Based on the average, the system usability was evaluated as marginal, but not acceptable. The result indicates that system usability should be closely analysed and improved.

4.2.2 The second prototype evaluation results

The test for the second prototype was organised on November 30, 2023, in VTT's XR laboratory and four users from KALMAR participated in the test.

The test users were generally satisfied with the second prototype. It was concluded by the users, that with this system, it could be already possible to operate the reach stacker. In terms of implemented camera views, three of the four camera angles (cabin, top-down, rear) were seen as appropriate for remote operation, while the added value of the bird's eye (drone) view was more difficult to see for the users. For getting the overview of the surroundings it would be however useful. It was also pointed out, that the rear camera view is necessary when the operator is driving the machine, but in the automated driving scenario it is less useful. For the improvement of camera views, the possibility to tailor the camera view combinations according to operator preferences was suggested. Furthermore, there should be a possibility to move cabin view camera to a desired position so that all the edges of the container are visible.

The existing XR features were mainly seen as suitable for the operation. The users suggested additional specific features for improving operator's experience, such as traffic light indicators (red-yellow-green) showing the status of twist locks (open / locked) and reach stacker grabber contact with the container. This was considered as an important feature because it is already in use and would provide a familiar experience for the operator. Furthermore, the current load chart was experienced as having a lot of information and it was suggested that it could be made simpler or to provide the option to hide it. However, the overload information and alert sign should be visible all the time.

The complete list of improvement suggestions related to cameras and XR features is presented in Table 6.

In terms of displays, a single display view was seen as easier to use and more suitable for experienced operator, while the power wall visualisation could serve less experienced persons and training purposes because of the more authentic experience.

Finally, it was discussed what kind of audio or haptics features could be implemented. It was suggested that adding real sounds on what is happening or might happen around the machine, such as shouts and sounds of collision, could be beneficial. Sounds would also indicate if there is something wrong with the machine. However, it was also pointed out that the idea of remote operation is that the operator does not have to hear everything all the time. It was also discussed if loud noise could be converted to some haptics.

#	Item	Specification
1	Traffic light indicators for twist locks and contact with the container	Traffic light indicators (red-yellow-green) showing the status of twist locks (open / locked) and reach stacker grabber's contact with the container.
2	Cabin view camera (cam1)	The cabin view camera should be relocated so that all the edges of the container are visible. Some cabin corners were blocking the view.
3	Cabin view (cam1) with improved XR-information visibility	Even though the same XR information is displayed on every camera view, it is less visible and harder to perceive in cabin view than in top-down view. It was suggested that arrows and circles showing position and twist lock status (etc.) should be better displayed in cabin view. It was pointed out that changing the cameras during operation might be hard and thus cabin view with improved XR-information visibility would be the ideal solution.
4	Wider rear view (cam3)	It was suggested that the rear view could be wider. (E.g., fisheye lens)

5	Overload / overweight alert sign	Some kind of simple indicator (meter) should tell the operator when the risk of overload is approaching. The overload alert sign should be visible all the time and it should be very clear.
6	Simplified load chart	The load chart was experienced as having a lot of information and it was suggested that it could be made simpler or to provide the option to remove it from the view. However, the overload alert sign must be visible all the time.
7	Standard spreader preset lengths	Standard preset lengths (20 feet / 40 feet) for the reach stacker spreader should also be added, there is already a button for selecting the length and a light indicator on the panel showing the length.
8	Tailored camera view combinations	The possibility to tailor the camera view combinations according to operator preferences was suggested.
9	Position of tyres	Position/direction of reach stacker tyres could be visualised / augmented.
10	Amount of throttle	Amount of reach stacker throttle could be visualised / augmented.

Table 6: Test users' improvement suggestions on the 2nd prototype.

SUS score average for the second prototype was **70** (N=4). Based on the average, the system usability was evaluated as acceptable. Three of the individual test participants' scores were in the acceptable range, while one participant evaluated the system usability as not acceptable. This was a clear improvement on the previous prototype.

4.2.3 The third prototype evaluation results

The third test of this development phase was organised on February 27, 2024, in VTT's XR laboratory and five test users from KALMAR participated in the test.

The users were satisfied with the system and the updates to the previous version. The XR-features were now seen as sufficient for moving on to the actual implementation phase. Due to large number of features in the prototype, it was mentioned that it would take some time to learn to use the system, for example to find the best combination of camera views. However, the possibility to tailor the camera views based on user preferences was seen as a useful feature. Furthermore, it was mentioned that the drone / bird's eye view would be great to have, but the actual implementation in the harbour environment would probably be difficult. For example, if the camera would be placed on top of the pole (or other high structure) instead of using a drone, the amount and location of suitable poles is crucial in terms of implementation.

The most important improvement suggestion was related to indicating the weight of the load and overload alert. Instead of showing the current load chart, a simpler meter indicating the status of the load was hoped for. An overload alert had already been implemented based on second prototype test results, but the meter should be visible all the time so that the operator can follow it constantly to avoid the overload.

The following other comments and suggestions emerged during the test:

- Weather settings: A (thick) fog would be good to visualise.
- Lidar view: This is an interesting feature, but the added value is currently hard to see. This would need further investigation and a use case.
- Direction / position of reach stacker tyres (visualised): This is relevant for rear tyres especially. The idea is that when the operator starts moving the reach stacker, he knows the direction of rear tyres with the help of visualisation. (Not very relevant for front tyres.)

SUS score average for the third prototype was **69** (N=5). Based on the average, the system usability was evaluated as acceptable. Four of the individual test participants' scores were in the acceptable usability

range, while one participant evaluated the system usability as marginal. Contrary to the previous prototype evaluations, none of the test users evaluated the system usability as not acceptable.

Figure 2: Power wall presentation of the 3rd prototype.

Figure 3: 3rd prototype drone view.

Haptics test results

Haption's device simulating a force-feedback-enabled joystick was also tested by the users. The users were able to try a force feedback feature when the simulated container touched the surface (e.g., ground, truck's bed). The test resulted in some positive reactions from the users. However, it was also suggested that touching the surface could possibly be better demonstrated with vibration feedback.

Further ideas and questions on how to utilise haptic features included the following:

- How to deliver a message of a very heavy load to the driver/operator with haptic features? That is, how to indicate, that *"this box is heavy, let's take it easy."* Haptic features could improve this experience better than for example only numbers.
- How to indicate the unbalance of the container with haptic features?

Figure 4: Haptics test with force-feedback-enabled joystick.

5 Use case 3 – Construction

5.1 Introduction

Seamless switching between excavation tasks and interacting with digital design models without relevant loss of time is considered the main challenge in introducing advanced digital systems in heavily manually operated machines such as excavators. Augmenting XR technologies that are capable to provide information in more natural and intuitive ways are considered to provide substantial potential to mitigate workload and usability issues in this regard.

Application of KPIs:

Regarding KPI 1.1 (improved safety for operator, vehicle, cargo and personnel in the area of operation): Excavators have significant issues in providing a good surround view and awareness to operators. Also, accuracy is highly limited by visual cues in the environment and the operators' skill. Conducted observations of operators revealed that state-of-the-art 3D machine models and their terminal-based user interfaces are not used to their full extent and their visual presentation of assistive information do not blend very well with the environment focused attention of operators. In bringing such information closer to the field of view, utilizing peripheral sight and enriching abstract visualizations of digital data and models with more natural visual cues in terminal-based user interfaces is considered to improve the operators' situational awareness and thus overall operation safety.

Regarding KPI 1.2 (reassured usability): Whereas operators are highly trained and familiarized with manual controls and interpreting real visual cues in the environment, today's terminal user interfaces often lack intuitive and easy ways to navigate and present additional digital data. We found that this is mainly because of excavator operators have little experience in navigating in complex graphical user interfaces and in using and manipulating 3D data of machines and terrain. We address this issue in redesign information presentation using more familiar visual cues using XR technologies and in simplifying interaction with them through less complex interaction techniques and more comprehensible visualisation techniques. This is considered to affect usability perception of operators and increasing their ability and willingness to use such systems.

Regarding KPI 1.3 (consideration of privacy): Preliminary analysis of safety concerns have been conducted to create awareness to this sensitive topic. Checking and ensuring the fulfilment of high privacy standards is ensured within WP3 and involves the application of privacy guidelines and checklists. We also identified key areas of ethical and privacy concerns in the case and validated them through extensive discussion with stakeholders-developers (N = 12) and operators N = 3.

Regarding KPI 1.4 (improved quality of work): The key motivation in presenting advanced digital data to machine operators is to improve accuracy, reduce operation errors that contribute to production performance. In easing interaction and improving information presentation, XR technologies are considered to improve quality of work by faster interaction time, higher acceptance and overall usage of digital data contributing to a better digging accuracy and work speed.

5.2 Prototype evaluation

Focus of XR prototypes:

Enhancing obstacle detecting and improving information presentation of area clearance as well as improving accessibility and interaction performance with 3d machine models and related data were identified as key field to implement XR technologies in user interfaces for excavators. So far, this resulted in an general interaction concept comprising of different integration and information presentation features that are (1) a peripheral light feedback system for obstacles, tool positioning and machine warnings, (2) a visualization of target surface of profile and real-time deviations, (3) a visual indicator located at the boom above the shovel for tool positioning and obstacle warning, (4) an enhanced 3D machine visualization to be displayed on a terminal, and (5) the implementation of advanced sensing and obstacle detection technologies to feed these systems. For all of them, prototypes of several fidelity stages have been realized and first expert-based user tests have been conducted. Where a first learning was successfully derived, these prototypes are continuously refined as we learned that these novel interaction approaches require a high level of usability, accuracy, and interactivity to make their potential visible.

Evaluation activities:

Parallel to the development of XR user interface features and associated sensor technology and data computation, four evaluation activities have been conducted so far:

1. Evaluating augmenting visualizations of surface mappings
2. Evaluating visual representations in the ambient light system in our interaction lab
3. Testing visibility and performance of the ambient light system in our test vehicle
4. Testing visual styles, visibility and assistive performance of the boom matrix display

5.2.1 Lab-based evaluation of surface mappings

Creating accurate pit geometries in excavation missions is key in modern construction sites to improve seamless integration between different construction phases. Today, virtual models that represent target profiles and periodic measures of resulting surface profiles generate useful data to inform operators about the quality of their work. However, their integration in terminal-based user interfaces is not optimal to support operators in their manual control activities. We found in expert interviews, that the visual discrepancy between reality and digital 3D visualizations is a pivotal issue that impairs effectivity of these types of assistance. So far, we explored different visual and technical approaches to provide a more augmented presentation of surface data to the operator. Figure 5 shows different visualization types that represent deviations from target height at each data point. As digital overlays also impair the perception of the real environment, information presentation must consider the trade-off between visibility and concealment. In exploring XR optimized visualization forms, we created prototypes for different grid forms and information mappings (e.g., dot size, colour, dot movement, dot form). All variations were evaluated regarding visibility and area concealment in a lab-based environment using a beamer projection in a dark room. So far, we found that dot-based grids are better than line grids but require high levels of brightness to

be detected reliably. We also found that changes in states require a substantial change in visual appearance as slight changes in size and colour easily go unnoticed in projected visualizations on soil surfaces.

In exploring a technical realization of this visualization approach, we started testing laser-projections using a class-4 laser projector (<https://www.laseros.com/de/lasercube/>) in the lab and in the experimental hall where our test vehicle is stationed. Even though the laser was capable to provide required brightness, the way it projects images is not optimized to project dot grids. Also, a laser that powerful represents a severe safety hazard for bystanders. As alternative environment-projections, we are currently working on a display-based video-augmentation that uses the same visualization techniques. However, our work continues to improve visualizations, ready for laser projection and display-based video augmentation. A key finding was that such visual overlay should be adaptable by allowing operators to adjust granularity (e.g., grid spacing and brightness) to seamlessly shift between “pure” environment and “full” digital augmentation.

Figure 5: Two different visual approaches to project height deviation to target surface profile in the interaction lab utilizing a beamer projection

5.2.2 Lab-based evaluation of the light feedback system

Elaborating on the potential and implementation of ambient light feedback to utilize peripheral vision as an additional perception modality explored many design dimensions of light feedback to map position, type and behaviour of detected obstacles.

Several approaches covering position in the cabin, information mapping on light parameters (e.g., colour, brightness) and light behaviour (determined animation) were identified. Positioning of the light feedback mainly focussed criteria such as visibility and distraction that may affect perceived usability. Two locations (around the front window, around the display terminal, see Figure 6) and four arrangements (Big O, Big U, small O and small U, also Figure 6) were prototyped. All options were prototyped in the interaction lab at Technische Universität Dresden for a first evaluation.

Regarding the visual form of the light feedback, many versions were explored altering form (dot, stripe, dashed line), colour, and size to represent different information about the detected obstacle. Finally, mapping obstacle-related information on these design dimensions of light feedback also resulted in a variety of designs (e.g., changing size, gap distance in dashed lines, brightness or colour to respond to the distance of the obstacle). Additionally, a version that uses two separate parallel light strips was created to test for a higher resolution of information mapping.

A selected set of variations was implemented in a dynamic prototype that was able to visualize five independently moving obstacles around the machine to compare each version regarding the criteria of intuitiveness of mapping, visibility (especially regarding detectability of changes), visual clutter and

perception quality of peripheral sight. This prototype setup was used to discuss and identify superior configuration in an expert workshop comprising a usability-based questionnaire to determine visual and comprehensive quality of each characteristic.

Figure 6: Different positions for the light feedback systems around the front window and the display terminal.

As a result, the small U shape was selected to most visible. Also, a preferred size, and preferred mapping configuration (change of size for distance, colour for object type) and behaviour of light signals for proximity warning could be identified. An important observation was the need to adjust the feedback as different expert preferred different settings, and familiarization changed feedback preferences. We are currently working on an improved version of the prototype that allows to change information mappings and feedback salience to allow for a more seamless evaluation. This also involves connecting the light feedback system to a virtual machine simulation with dynamic objects in the environment.

5.2.3 Test vehicle-based evaluation of the light feedback system

After the first test round that confirmed the beneficial potential of peripheral light feedback, a first version of the system was implemented in our test vehicle (a Case excavator) in Dresden to verify visibility under real condition.

The implemented system used the small U shape setup on the front screen of the vehicle. It was connected to a camera-based object detection system to visualize near-by objects in real time. A first performance test yielded promising results as the system behaved as intended giving precise feedback about position, type and behaviour of several objects. This evaluation step proved the technical feasibility of the system. In further extending the systems capabilities, improved visualization, mappings and animations will be implement in the near future. We also aim to implement adaptation functionalities that allow the operator to manipulate the light feedback according to his needs, when it passes the lab-based test procedure.

5.2.4 Technical test of the matrix-display

Whereas the development of the light feedback system started in the lab, the matrix-display (see Figure 7) was first implemented in the test vehicle using a retail hardware component. It was connected to the machine's digital twin to become reactive to the tool's actual position. This setup was used to test visibility as it is located in close proximity to the tool and thus can be fairly far away from the operator in the cabin. The first testing resulted in very promising results regarding the brightness of the display but also constraints regarding the resolution of the visualized cues. After the first hardware test, a design iteration took place that developed different visualization approaches to use the matrix display to visualize positive and negative deviations between current tool position and target surface profile. This resulted in an update for the visuals used in the matrix display as it was found that switching between a rough and fine mode is required to provide enough accuracy in fine grading manoeuvres. This current design (see Figure 8) was integrated into the vehicle-mounted system and yielded improved usability among a small sample (2) of test drivers. In the meantime, a second setup of the matrix-display was built in the interaction lab utilizing a 10-inch tablet to develop and test further visualization styles and the implementation of other information (e.g., position of objects under the surface). As a result, good visibility technical functionality of the feedback could be achieved.

Figure 7: Implemented light feedback system and matrix display in the test vehicle at Technische Universität Dresden

Figure 8: Preferred visualization of height deviation from target surface for the matrix display with a resolution of 16 by 16 pixels.

5.2.5 Further activities

More iterations on the presented techniques and technologies are planned throughout this project year. Also new XR features are planned such as window projection and especially interaction techniques and devices to adapt each XR feature to situation-based needs. We continue to use both demonstration setups (our-lab based cabin mock-up, and the test vehicle) to implement XR features as feasible. In the end, both demonstrators need to implement a realistic task setting to reliably measure perceived usability, quality of work, situation awareness, acceptance and to argue upon safety improvements. Whereas the test vehicle will pursue this in implementing the XR features into the real machine data infrastructure to test these in actual digging tasks, the lab-based demonstrator will implement a virtual machine simulation.

6 Conclusions

Throughout all use cases, first prototypes were built to explore effective means of XR technologies in machine operation. These prototypes were already used for technical and functional testing regarding previously identified requirements and KPIs. Technical tests, expert workshops and user studies provided feedback that is currently used to refine our XR interaction concepts and technical solutions that will be implemented into next iterations of prototypes. This feedback is already used to further improve design and performance of our XR technologies and user interface features.

In all three use cases, the utilization of XR environments combined with human-centric evaluation and design methodologies has proven to be a powerful approach for improved operation performance, also indicating the potential to booster user experience and usability. The conducted evaluation activities overall confirmed the usefulness of our approaches for cabin-based and remote operation of mobile machines.

Testing phase so far covered, a panoramic thermal-RGB camera, a camera-based spotlight system, a novel laser-camera setup, a display-based VR control environment, gaze and hand gesture-based interaction, advanced haptic controller feedback, orthogonal camera views, ambient light feedback and tool-mounted matrix displays in lab and field-based testing procedures. Technical functionality and feasibility could be established for almost all prototypes, except the laser projection test in broad daylight in the excavator tests. Also, usefulness for all XR approaches could be verified. The potential of our approach to implement XR feedback in real environments and information presentation devices was underscored as some users expressed discomfort when using an HMD and instead indicated a preference to use displays and real-world augmentation. First usability tests for some XR feature supported our approaches and their suitability for machine operation.

However, testing also revealed needs for further improvement as test participants for example the required gaze in hand-tracked menus in the VR environment, the fidelity of the prototypes (e.g., VR camera substitutes, implementation of LiDAR data). Also due to large number of features in all prototypes, it was mentioned that it would take some time to learn to use the system, for example to find the best combination of camera views. Our final evaluation activities will account for this issue by implementing several stages of testing with the same participant.

Based on these findings, the main design choices for the next design cycle should prioritize AR-based visualization on the power wall, real camera footage traffic light indicators (red-yellow-green) for tool status, simpler and adaptable visual presentation of additional information (e.g., load charts for the reach stacker), single display views instead of multi-display views in the teleoperation use case, audio and haptic feedback, and the inclusion of additional information (e.g., load and overload alert in container handling, hidden objects in the construction pit).

In the next phase of development, we focus on reaching higher levels of fidelity allowing for comprehensive test scenarios with real machine operators to conduct more rigor performance and usability evaluations. This will also include larger user studies that provide more significant and reliable implications regarding the quality of our development results.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

CWS	Collision Warning Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SUS	System Usability Scale
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality